

USE OF MANAGEMENT TERMINOLOGY IN A GLOBALISED WORLD. BEYOND AN APPARENT TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract

Purpose – *The aim of the authors of the article is to identify trends in the use of managerial specialist language in its operation and expression in the current global context, with its widely accepted attributes of volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity. Subsequently, for such a topic, which is very rarely dealt with explicitly in the literature, it is desirable to identify the extent to which a standard, classical general language is being preserved and, complementarily, what are the sources of change (renewal, transformation of meaning, internationalization, regionalization, abandonment of certain concepts, etc.).*

Methodology/approach – *The research is carried out by highlighting specific aspects of the topic already manifested in the literature and practice. Various approaches found in the literature are explored. In addition, interviews of prestigious international personalities in the field of management are selected and bibliometrically analyzed in order to identify frequencies of use of certain terms and to highlight possible conceptual convergences and new trends in management terminology.*

Findings – *Globalization, and in particular the economic component, is causing changes in managerial conceptualization and expression. Important influencing factors, in terms of intensity and extent, are the digitalization of processes and the contemporary internationalization of business.*

Research limitations/implications – *The scope and validation of the findings is limited by the possibility to investigate exhaustively, in large groups, nationally and internationally, at the level of specialists and everyday language, young people and adults, etc. the ways in which contemporary management terminology is used. The diversity of areas in which management knowledge is applied should also be considered as a limitation.*

Practical implications – *The usefulness of such research can be manifested both at the academic level (how we form and cultivate a topical managerial culture, relevant to the practical work of organizations but also in terms of temporality) and at the level of organizations and business (through the need for a minimum level of semantic interoperability).*

Originality/value – *Scanning the literature produced strictly on this topic reveals an insignificant concern in terms of popularized results. Implicitly, the topic has been marginally addressed in some complementary works as a framing of the subject. This can be seen as a direction for studies and research at the national level in interdisciplinary teams (at least in fields such as linguistics and economics), the aim being to bring the topic into line with international managerial realities.*

Key words: *management, terminology, globalization.*

1. Introduction to the general framework of the proposed topic

Management has progressed in recent times (the early 2000s can be taken as a benchmark) in terms of the content of specific processes, but also in terms of scope and issues covered. From an academic point of view, in addition to the classical component, often referred to as “the basics of management”, we are seeing the emergence of new trends, new meanings of concepts and different authors (from different geographical areas) who are becoming increasingly known for their approaches. The above-mentioned management foundations are becoming more comprehensive, allocating more space to emerging concepts, changing the very idea of the base, the foundation, in a narrow, limiting, restrictive sense, moving to a more flexible and permissive approach for the growth of the conceptual managerial heritage of reference. The conceptual basis of the scientific foundation of management is becoming increasingly broad, influenced, of course, by the increasingly diversified links with the practice.

Globalization, a long-standing process but with ever-changing forms of manifestation, has also brought with it challenges in the field of management. Stephen P. Robbins and Mary Coulter (2016, p. 144) point out that “As we look at managing in today’s global environment, we want to focus on two important issues. The first issue involves the challenges associated with globalization, especially in relation to the openness that is part of being global. The second issue revolves around the challenges of managing a “global workforce”. We have linked the main topic of the article to globalization because we believe that this is the main framework that has provided, in terms of space and time, the premises for the development of contemporary management and, implicitly, of current terminology. Digitization facilitates knowledge in the field of management and in the sense of acceptance in management of more and more concepts specific to IT, thus reaching some associations that were impossible 20 years ago, such as digital leadership (Espina-Romero, Noroño Sánchez, Rojas-Cangahuala, Palacios Garay, Parra, Rio Corredoira, 2023) or digital management (Khorsand, Peráček, 2023). Globalization has of course imposed a certain level of freedom in all areas of social and professional life, and so it was an irreversible process in management as well. In the early 2000s, Professor Abrudan Ioan (2012, p. 28) drew attention, however, to the need to find a certain balance in the specific conceptualizations of management at national level: “I am not an advocate of popularizing management through abusive associations and [...] I will not support the concepts of *literary* management or management in who knows what field for which life has already consecrated a term understood by everyone, but I argue that the current space of meaning allocated to management, is too narrow and begins to become suffocating, and those who manage it are too few in relation to the real manifestations of the *phenomenon of management* and in relation to the expectations of the Romanian public”. Talking about the terms management and leadership invoked before, will it not be long before we will also see the use of *leaderment* and *managership*?

Terminology is the total body of words and concepts specific to a field, in this case management. There are differences of approach, in the sense of specialization, which subsequently becomes internationalized, of terms including at national level, depending on the dominant industry in a country. For example, one can identify a specialization of terminology in the field of quality management in Japan, which is subsequently borrowed and used in other countries. The same can be said for production management, which is specifically addressed as a high specialization of processes, and therefore of terminology, for Germany. At the level of the Romanian school of management, the idea and publication of a management dictionary, coordinated and published in 2011 by the reputed specialist Ovidiu Nicolescu, with the participation of numerous specialists from national university centers, is welcome. However, it is also necessary, simply because of its timeframe, to republish it at the same time as updating the terms.

From a methodological point of view, which is presented in detail in the next section, in order to investigate the use of managerial language, the top ten known authors listed on <https://globalgurus.org/management-gurus-top-30/> were selected, documents (.doc format)

with interviews given by them were generated and processed for each of them and integrated with QDAminer software (useful for qualitative analysis).

2. Studies and research on contemporary management terminology

One trend that has emerged is the looseness with which synonymous terms for a given concept are used and accepted to a fairly large extent. This is seen both in the academic world (see contemporary scientific research) and in everyday practice. Figure 1 illustrates this for the concept of entrepreneurship. In a training session on digital education held at the authors' home institution, when asked to indicate associations for entrepreneurship, the following semantic variants were indicated among the 18 responses: business, initiative, developer, freedom of action, management.

Fig. 1. Synonymous expression possibilities for entrepreneurship
Source: Authors

The evolution of terminology is peculiar to countries that for various reasons (often due to dictatorial political-military regimes) have not had access to a diversified management literature. Coupled with the lack of a free market economy, the conditions for the development of specific language have been severely limited. The development of managerial terminology can be directly related to the democratically based economic development of a state. Economic dynamics, both at the national level and in international trade relations, also determine the dynamics of specific vocabulary and the pressure for change or renewal. This is also the case of some neologisms recently accepted in the Romanian explanatory dictionary (e.g. business). The need to popularize managerial terminology so as to create semantic interoperability is also highlighted by the large number of internet resources, some of them produced by professional organizations themselves, which provide those interested with the most common or most frequently used terms and their explanations. At the level of academic literature, more specifically in the case of management manuals or handbooks, some of which have reached more than 15 global editions, comparing in the same gap of about 20 years, we

observe a diffusion of the concepts exposed and a much better expressed link to the diverse realities of the contemporary world (example - diversity management, social responsibility management, operations management, etc.). In fact, all the processes linked to the ITC industry and digitization are a real factor in the change in management terminology, both in terms of diversity and intensity of change. The issue must be seen in two senses, both in terms of the role played by the ITC industry and digitization in changing business processes and their role (and potential for change) in managerial communication.

The following are the main features of the use of managerial terminology as they emerge from the qualitative research undertaken.

Based on a ranking by <https://globalgurus.org/> of the top 30 best management professionals in the world in 2024, we tried to identify the current trend of topics and directions of action by analyzing the terms used in public speeches. The analysis focused on the top 10 professionals in the hierarchy and their speeches were analyzed using the qualitative data analysis tool, QDA Miner.

Fig. 2. Word Cloud based on Bob Nelson’s speeches
 Source: Authors, own processing in QDA Miner

Dr. Bob Nelson’s track record as president of his own management consulting and training company, which specializes in helping organizations improve their management practices, programs and systems, makes him one of the world’s leading experts on employee motivation, performance, engagement, recognition and reward. Thus, analyzing Figure 2, based on the analysis of Bob Nelson’s speeches, confirms the concern for employees, human resources in general, new motivation strategies, trends adapted to the global context and the practical reality in which organizations operate.

Barbara Kellerman is a leadership specialist and founding executive director of the Center for Public Leadership at the Harvard Kennedy School. Barbara Kellerman has given speeches and seminars to audiences around the world and is considered a pioneer in the field of leadership and followership. Figure 10 highlights the ideas she highlights in her speeches. We highlight terms such as leadership, people, leaders, time, followers, studies, school, books, college, etc. Barbara Kellerman is the author and editor of a considerable number of books, which she constantly quotes in her speeches.

Fig. 11. Word Cloud based on Herminia Ibarra’s speeches
Source: Authors, own processing in QDA Miner

A recognized specialist in leadership, Herminia Ibarra is Professor of organizational behavior at London Business School, with a focus on analyzing career development pathways. It can be seen from Fig. 11 that she is concerned with career, leadership, people, work, professional, time, while also touching on reinvention, identity, change, perspectives, authenticity, behaviors, skills, reflections, etc. There is a multitude of terms used to outline, as defined in one of her most successful books, *Strategii neconvenționale pentru reinventarea carierei [Unconventional Strategies for Career Reinvention]*.

Fig. 12. Common elements in the speeches of the management specialists analyzed
Source: Authors, own processing in QDA Miner

Fig. 12 highlights the common terms used by the 10 specialists, considered management gurus. They are highly professional in their activities (teaching, scientific writing, consultancy, company management) and all share a common concern to improve management practice and theory through people and leadership. This objective is joined by action areas such as marketing, strategy, innovation, market, research, implementation, career, customer. Recognition of the quality in these speeches comes from the results achieved by organizations that have implemented the ideas and strategies they promote. Starting from a common overall objective, they have achieved performance by developing ideas and directions for development based on different concepts and methods.

Discussions and conclusions

Globalization is a factor in the internationalization of management terminology. We are talking here about both the borrowing of concepts into management practice and their formalization in a country's vocabulary. As the English language has been an instrument of communication across the physical borders of a country, a part of the specialized vocabulary in management originates along these lines. The existence of large companies, with subsidiaries in different countries, has favored the use and transformation of management terminology in the sense described above.

Depending on the major area of practical and academic concern of the authors analyzed in terms of the terminology used, the frequency of certain terms also takes precedence in the case of each author. The integration of the ten working papers produced specifically for each author, followed by their analysis with QMiner, highlights the terms frequently used in management, trending in the current global context. The people orientation is also noted here, which is also in line with current management realities, with some interventions supporting the (re)humanization of management.

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